

Anuvadini as an AI-Based Tool: A User-Centered Quantitative Evaluation**Sadiya Shaheen,***Research Scholar,**Department of Teacher Training & Non-formal Education (IASE),**Faculty of Education, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi,**shaheen.0279@gmail.com***Kulsoom Reza,***Research Scholar,**Department of Teacher Training & Non-formal Education (IASE),**Faculty of Education, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi,**kulsoomreza02@gmail.com***Dr. Aerum Khan,***Associate Professor,**Department of Teacher Training & Non-formal Education (IASE),**Faculty of Education, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi,**akhan26@jmi.ac.in***ABSTRACT**

Artificial Intelligence powered translation tools are increasingly used in educational and research domains. They have helped in overcoming language barriers and enhancing accessibility. This paper evaluates the usability and performance of India's AI powered translation tool, Anuvadini. Data was collected from participants using a self-constructed questionnaire. The study examined five key dimensions: Translation Quality, User Interface, Language Support, Processing Speed, and Applicability in educational and research settings. Pie charts are used to present the research findings. The participants' responses show variability across different evaluated parameters. There was a general positive response towards Anuvadini's translation quality and applicability. On the other hand, website design and language expansion require further improvement. Overall, Anuvadini has proven highly beneficial in multilingual learning for people with diverse backgrounds. The study highlights the need for improved user training and integration of such tools in the academic journey of students. This paper helps in increased adoption of AI tools in the Indian education system.

Keywords: Anuvadini, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Educational Technology, language support, higher education, India.

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INTRODUCTION

The rapid emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is reshaping every domain of modern society. It has helped various sectors to smoothly operate and flourish immensely. AI has redefined the conventional way in which business, transportation, healthcare etc used to flourish. amongst all these sectors comes the education sector, which has seen tremendous transformation. integration of the intelligent technologies into education has made it more interactive, inclusive and personalised (Rane et al., 2023). Transition can be seen how knowledge is created, delivered and understood. The integration of AI in education has a great potential for both students and teachers (Ahuja & Bala, 2021). In a country like India where students come from different linguistic backgrounds, Anuvadini has emerged as a significant AI tool to remove this barrier. The Union Ministry has made it compulsory for all educational institutions to develop textbooks in regional languages (Baboo, R., & Rawat, S., 2025). It also emphasised that students could think more critically if they are studying in their own regional language (Sinclair et al., 2020). Anuvadini has potential to comply with these directives efficiently. NEP 2020 has also planned to integrate digital resources with different regional languages. It is believed that developing multilingual learning materials (Mohanty, A. K. 2009) can create a new generation of multidisciplinary learners (Bhattacharjee, 2025). According to Srivastava (2024), Anuvadini provides a wide range of features such as document translation capabilities and speech messengers. It provides translation services for documents, texts, speeches, images, and videos. The application supports 22 Indian and 37 foreign languages which will bring national as well as international cooperation. The main beneficiaries are students, teachers, researchers, lifelong learners and educational institutions. This application is quite different from Google Translate because it is tailored to Indian languages. Moreover, it provides easier synonyms of English technical terms to aid comprehension and facilitate the learning process.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A study found that AI powered translation apps including Anuvadini helps in promoting inclusivity. It helps teachers to effectively communicate in multilingual classrooms. There is dire need of training students on responsible use of such applications. It is equally important for policymakers, teachers and parents to integrate such technologies in mainstream education (Torty, 2025). Another study revealed that AI applications enhance translation efficiency and help users to improve their vocabulary and grammar. It also provides editing support, professional and technical support, personalization, and pedagogical innovation. (Nguyen et al., 2025). It's been noted that such

AI powered translating applications serve as means of linguistic preservation (Krishna et al., 2025). The applications such as Bhashini and Anuvadini facilitate digital vernacular language (Districk & Nadu, 2025). Anuvadini is effective in translating educational content for students and regional institutions. (Wadhawan, 2023). A study has noted that in Indian rich linguistic diversity, the language barrier prevents many bright students from excelling in the STEM fields (Batty & Reilly, 2022). Anuvadini's application has solved this problem. It has translated B.Tech textbooks into multiple regional languages and has helped in introducing undergraduate and diploma courses in Telugu, Hindi, and Kannada in many institutions (Agarwal, 2022). It has also been used to translate course content and resources from SWAYAM and IGNOU into other languages. In school education, there is a major issue of school dropouts (Kurian et al., 2023) due to students' language difficulties. This application has potential to reduce such dropouts.

Overview of some of the Anuvadini's features

Anuvadini is Government of India's first AI based voice and document translation application. It aims to achieve NEP's vision of integrating technology in teaching learning processes as well as language translation. It supports 22 regional and foreign languages to unify India and the world under the principles of 'Ek Bharat Shrestha Bharat' and 'One Earth, One Family, One Future'. The main features of Anuvadini are shown in figure 1 below. Some of its features are discussed in detail below.

1. Ananta

This feature supports documents in .doc, .txt, .pptx and .pdf formats and converts the content into selected language. It also allows users to interact with the documents. It also combines documents to provide comprehensive understanding of the material. Language support is provided in several languages as shown in figure 2.

Figure 1. Various features of Anuvadini available on its website

Figure 2. Interface of Anuvadini’s Ananta

2. Bharat Audio Live

This feature connects people across India by translating voices into different languages. A fisherman in Andhra Pradesh can speak Telugu, and his words are heard in Punjabi by a farmer in Punjab. The platform also provides written transcripts to help learners and the deaf. It celebrates India’s diversity by bringing everyone’s voice together in one place. It supports a wide range of national and international languages such as English, Assamese, Hindi, Telugu, Tamil, Kannada, Odia, Malayalam, Marathi, Gujarati, Bengali, Urdu, Punjabi, Russian, Spanish, Chinese, French, Arabic, Portuguese, Sundanese, German, Japanese, Korean, Italian, Turkish, Malay, Czech, Swedish, Filipino, Romanian, Serbian, Dutch, Greek, Hebrew, Polish, Indonesian, Finnish, Thai, Hungarian, and Bulgarian as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. Interface of Anuvadini’s Bharat Audio Live

3. Bhashin

Bhashin uses voice translation features in the user's preferred language as shown in the figure 4. The user's speech is recorded and the same text appears on the screen in the selected language. After choosing the preferred voice gender and target language for translation, the AI generates translated audio. This output can be downloaded as an audio file in .wav format.

Figure 4. Interface of Anuvadini's Bhashin

4. Virtual Keyboard for Indian Languages

This keyboard helps users type in multiple Indian languages smoothly and accurately. It supports typing even if their physical keyboard does not support those scripts. Users can type in English letters and the application converts it automatically into Indian language as shown in the figure 5.

Figure 5. Interface of Anuvadini's Virtual Keyboard

User's feedback of Anuvadini

This survey has used a descriptive design to assess user's perceptions of Anuvadini. The main focus was to know user's experiences across five dimensions such as Translation Quality, User Interface, Language Support, Processing Speed, Applicability. Two items were added under each dimension. A total of 87 participants from different professional and educational backgrounds responded through google form. Findings of each parameter are discussed in detail.

1. Translation Quality:

When asked if translations provided by Anuvadini are clear and precise, 40.5% of the users agreed and 17.9% strongly agreed. While 36.9% remained neutral, the remaining disagreed with the statement as shown in figure 6. When asked if the text generated by Anuvadini preserves the original meaning of the content, 44.7% of the users agreed and 14.1% strongly agreed as shown in figure 7. 4.8% disagreed with the statement whereas 36.9% remained neutral. Overall, the findings suggest that Anuvadini performs effectively as a translation support tool in educational and professional contexts.

Figure 6. User responses on the clarity and precision of translations generated by Anuvadini.

Figure 7. User responses on the extent to which Anuvadini preserves the original meaning of the source content during translation.

2. User Interface:

Out of 87 participants, 44.6% agreed that Anuvadini's interface is user friendly and easy to navigate. 18.1% strongly agreed with the statement, 34.9% remained neutral and the remaining disagreed with the statement as shown in figure 8. When they were asked if its icon and instructions were easy to understand without external help, 65.4% of users responded positively. Figure 9 shows 32.1% remained neutral and the rest of the participants disagreed. The general feedback reflects a positive perception. This shows the users can use Anuvadini independently and perceive its interface as user friendly.

Figure 8. User responses regarding the user-friendliness and ease of navigation of Anuvadini's interface.

Figure 9. User responses on the clarity of Anuvadini's icons and instructions for independent use.

3. Language Support:

When asked if Anuvadini provides translation features in a wide range of national and international languages relevant for their needs, 45.9% of the users agreed and 16.5% strongly agreed. 28.2% remained neutral and the remaining disagreed with the statement as shown in figure 10. When asked if the translation accuracy of Anuvadini is consistent and reliable, 40% of the users agreed and 14.1% strongly agreed as shown in figure 11. 8.2% disagreed with the statement whereas 36.5% remained neutral. Overall the responses highlighted the strong capability of Anuvadini in handling multiple Indian languages. It is useful for users from different linguistic backgrounds.

Figure 10. User responses regarding the availability of a wide range of national and international languages in Anuvadini.

Figure 11. User responses on the consistency and reliability of translation accuracy provided by Anuvadini.

4. Processing Speed:

When asked if Anuvadini deals with heavy files quickly and efficiently, 38.1% of the users agreed and 20.2% strongly agreed. 36.9% remained neutral and the rest disagreed with the statement as shown in figure 12. When asked if the processing speed of audio outputs meets their expectations, 41.2% of the users agreed and 17.6% strongly agreed as shown in figure 13. 35.6% remained neutral while the rest of the participants disagreed with the statement. Overall the responses highlighted Anuvadini delivers outputs in a timely manner.

Figure 12. User responses regarding Anuvadini's efficiency in handling and processing large files.

Figure 13. User responses on users' satisfaction with the processing speed of audio outputs generated by Anuvadini.

5. Applicability:

When asked if Anuvadini is appropriate for academic tasks such as studying and understanding learning materials, 41.2% of the users agreed and 15.3% strongly agreed. 38.8% remained neutral and the remaining disagreed with the statement as shown in figure 14. When asked if Anuvadini is appropriate for different professional tasks, 37.2% of the users agreed and 20.9% strongly agreed as shown in figure 15. 37.2% remained neutral whereas the rest of the participants disagreed with this statement. Overall, the responses show that Anuvadini has a wide applicability. Its features such as speech-to-text and document translation are very helpful for different professions as well as students.

Figure 14. User responses regarding the suitability of Anuvadini for various academic tasks

Figure 15. User responses regarding the suitability of Anuvadini for various professional tasks in different fields.

Conclusion:

The study provides a detailed evaluation of Anuvadini tool. It highlights its features, capabilities and overall effectiveness. It has examined five dimensions including Translation quality, User interface, Language support, Processing speed and Applicability. It has shown strong performance and user satisfaction across all these dimensions. Users reported that it provides clear translations while keeping the original meaning of content intact. This feature proves its reliability as a translation tool. The interface is found easy to navigate. Users don't need much guidance to operate it smoothly. The availability of numerous national and international languages makes it more accessible to everyone. In a country like India, users from different linguistic backgrounds can benefit from it. Its audio and video translation feature, CV writing support, and handwritten AI fulfill the needs of students, teachers, researchers and different professionals. The users acknowledged its ability to smoothen communication across different languages and support professional workflows.

Overall, Anuvadini serves as a technologically advanced and user centered AI tool. It effectively bridges language barriers and supports academic as well as professional tasks. Despite this, there remains need for further improvement to maximize its engagement and familiarity. The study confirms it is a transformative tool in education, research and professional practice. It significantly contributes to a more efficient and inclusive learning ecosystem in India.

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